

The implementation of national learning camp (NLC) in elementary schools of tabaco city

Annabel Bonayon Buendia *

MAED Major in Administration and Supervision, Daniel B. Pena Memorial College Foundation Inc.

International Journal of Science and Research Archive, 2025, 14(03), 1372-1376

Publication history: Received on 23 February 2025; revised on 28 March 2025; accepted on 31 March 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/ijrsra.2025.14.3.0926>

Abstract

This quantitative study examined the implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) in Elementary Schools of Tabaco City for SY 2023 – 2024. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

- What is the status of implementation of National Learning Camp in elementary schools of Tabaco City Division along: (a) teacher volunteer; (b) teaching methodologies; (c) stakeholders' engagement; and (d) learning resources?
- Is there a significant difference on the status of implementation of National Learning Camp in elementary schools between numeracy and literacy along the areas?
- What are the effects of the implementation of the National Learning Camp to the performance of the pupils along: (a) literacy; (b) numeracy?
- What are the problems encountered on the implementation of National Learning Camp (NLC)?
- What intervention plan may be proposed to address the problems?

The study utilized quantitative research methodology to determine the experiences of key stage 1 teachers in the elementary schools of Tabaco City Division. Data collected were gathered using a survey questionnaire. The process included three main steps: distribution of survey questionnaires, gathering data, analysis and interpretation of data. The study involved 210 key stage 1 teachers from the 39 public elementary schools and 1 integrated school of Tabaco City Division.

Findings: The findings of the study are:

- The overall implementation of National Learning Camp has obtained weighted means of 4.67 and 4.66 in numeracy and literacy respectively with descriptive rating of *Extremely Implemented*. Variables identified namely *Teacher Volunteer*, *Teaching Methodologies*, *Stakeholders' Engagement*, and *Learning Resources* have gained the weighted means of 4.69, 4.76 4.58, and 4.64 respectively in numeracy and 4.68, 4.73, 4.58, and 4.64 respectively in literacy and all having an *Extremely Implemented* descriptive rating.
- The F-computed values for all variables are lower than the tabular F-value of 5.32, indicating that these factors do not have a significant effect on the implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC).
- The NLC implementation to numeracy and literacy development among learners show significant impact. It was found out the NLC implementation has a *Very High* effect to *Numeracy* and *Literacy* skills development of learners garnering relatively close respective weighted means of 4.61 and 4.62.
- The respondents have confirmed the pre-identified problems along respective variables. Frequency count both in numeracy and literacy shows the following results: on *Teacher Volunteer*, problems perceived are *lack of training and seminars related to the implementation of National Learning Camp (NLC) program (94)*, *lack of*

* Corresponding author: Annabel Bonayon Buendia

collaborative expertise (29), and inadequate trained volunteer teachers to handle groupings (65); along Teaching Methodologies –absence of ICT integration (60), limited fun-based activities for learners (56), and lack of effective teaching practices to enhance the overall learning environment (48); with respect to Stakeholders' Engagement results was absence of parents' support towards learners' participation in NLC (102), lack of parents' attendance in the orientation of National Learning Camp orientation (90) and lack of other stakeholders' support in the school's implementation of National Learning Camp (83); and lastly with regards to Learning Resources survey resulted to insufficient funding support for the resources and materials (96), inadequate teaching materials for teachers (72), and lack of learning materials for students (62).

- A comprehensive intervention plan has been proposed to address the challenges encountered along NLC implementation. This proposed plan aims to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the program, ensuring its optimal execution in future implementations.

The result of this study will provide valuable insights to effectively implement the program, identify strengths and areas for improvement, and guide future educational strategies and policies. Additionally, the study highlights challenges faced by teachers, offering recommendations for better support and professional development programs. Furthermore, the study assists school administrators in understanding the resources required for successful implementation and ensures that pupils and teachers have the necessary tools for success. Finally, the study encourages greater community engagement, informing stakeholders about the status of the National Learning Camp (NLC) and fostering collaboration to improve educational outcomes.

Conclusion: From the findings stated above, the following conclusions were drawn.

- The National Learning Camp was *highly implemented* in the thirty-nine (39) public elementary schools and one (1) integrated school of Tabaco City Division. Key variables such as *Teacher Volunteer, Teaching Methodologies, Stakeholders' Engagement, and Learning Resources* all received *Extremely Implemented* ratings, further demonstrating the effectiveness and thoroughness of the program's implementation.
- There is no significant difference on the status of implementation National Learning Camp of the elementary school of Tabaco City Division between numeracy and literacy along the areas. Hence, numeracy and literacy were implemented complementary to each other considering teacher volunteer competence, learning resources and stakeholders' engagement.
- The implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) has had a significant and positive impact on the literacy and numeracy development among learner participants. With The findings indicated a *Very High* effect on enhancing these essential skills among the participants.
- The common problem encountered in each identified key areas namely *Teaching Methodologies, Stakeholders' Engagement, and Learning Resources* relative to numeracy and literacy are: (a) *lack of training and seminars related to the implementation of NLC program;* (b) *absence of ICT integration;* (c) *absence of parents' support towards learners' participation in NLC;* and *insufficient funding support for the resources and materials* respectively.
- A comprehensive intervention plan has been proposed to address the challenges encountered along NLC implementation. This proposed plan aims to enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of the program, ensuring its optimal execution in future implementations.

Recommendations: Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed to effectively implement and sustain the National Learning Camp (NLC):

- Based on the successful implementation of the National Learning Camp in the 40 public elementary schools of Tabaco City Division it is recommended to sustain and strengthen teachers' training, expand stakeholders' engagement, optimize learning resources and replicate best practices.
- With the equal importance paid on numeracy and literacy development of learners through the National Learning Camp implementation, intensification of these skill may be fostered through continuous integration in instruction towards critical numeracy and literacy.
- To further build the significant positive impact of the NLC on literacy and numeracy development among learners' program expansions, enhancement of targeted interventions and strategic monitoring and evaluation is recommended.
- To address the identified along identified key areas timely and relevant targeted training be provided among teachers; devise programs to promote parental involvement that raises awareness and encourages greater parental support for their children's participation to NLC; and establish partnership and linkages to advocate

for increase funding ensuring the availability of adequate resources and materials relative to NLC implementation.

- The proposed intervention plan to enhance inclusive education be evaluated, approved and recommended.

Areas for Further Study: The following areas are recommended for further research:

- School Head's Capacity to Support Teachers in Education Program Implementation
- Parental Capacity and Its Influence on Learner Performance
- Effectiveness of Teachers' Professional Development on Teacher Performance

Keywords: National Learning Camp (NLC); Program Implementation; Learning Resources; Literacy; Numeracy

1. Introduction

Education is a fundamental human right that every child deserves, as it plays a critical role in shaping their future and empowering them to fully participate in society. Yet, despite the global recognition of education as a universal right, disparities in access, quality, and outcomes continue to persist, particularly in marginalized and underserved areas.

A child's right to education entails the right to learn and ensure that children have access to quality education and skills development must be equitable and inclusive for all children and adolescents, regardless of who they are or where they live, and which lays the foundation for a brighter future. It opens doors to opportunities and empowers young minds to reach their full potential. Education generally relates to a person's life goals and future well-being.

Furthermore, education cultivates vital life skills, fosters an understanding of social norms, and helps students develop sound judgment and reasoning, enabling them to discern right from wrong. The importance of education extends beyond individual benefit; it is crucial for society. Its ultimate objective is to empower individuals to navigate life competently and contribute positively to their communities.

Learning gaps have emerged as a major challenge in the education system, exacerbated by the school closures and disruptions caused by the pandemic. These closures led to an unprecedented interruption in face-to-face instruction, leaving students without access to consistent learning experiences for extended periods. As a result, many students have fallen behind in key subjects, with some losing crucial foundational knowledge and skills. This gap in learning is particularly noticeable in vulnerable communities where access to online learning or alternative educational resources was limited, further widening the disparity between students of different socio-economic backgrounds.

Elementary education plays a critical role in shaping a child's cognitive, social, and emotional development. This stage is typically designed for children between the ages of 5 to 12 and lays the groundwork for future academic and personal growth. It's about preparing them not only for the next stage in their education but also for becoming well-rounded, curious, and responsible individuals. However, presently, many school-aged children are experiencing significant learning gaps, which have been exacerbated by the disruptions caused by the pandemic and other challenges.

Taking decisive action to accelerate the recovery from learning loss is essential for national education responses to the pandemic. To enable quick learning recovery, school systems must implement strategies that make instruction more effective, relevant, and relational, and ensure teachers can support the recovery process in the classrooms. Learning Recovery is an urgent call to bridge learning gaps.

Learning Recovery Programs can help tackle the learning losses caused by extended school closures, disruptions in the academic calendar, and uneven access to remote learning opportunities. The Philippines has consistently ranked among the lowest in international assessments, highlighting pervasive systemic issues within the three-education system. These assessments include the Program for International Student Assessment (PISA), Southeast Asia Primary Learning Metrics (SEAPLM), and Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS).

In the Philippines, education presents a multifaceted crisis that demands urgent attention. To understand the context in which the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP) operates, we must critically examine the complexity of this educational crisis. The most pressing issue is the widening learning gaps. A World Bank study has unveiled alarming statistics regarding education in the Philippines, indicating a significant deficiency in basic literacy skills crucial for further learning. This study estimates a learning gap of 5.5 years, suggesting that many students are significantly behind their appropriate educational attainment levels.

Considering these significant challenges, the Department of Education has launched DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2023 known as the National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP) represents a comprehensive and strategic approach to addressing learning loss and improving educational outcomes across the Philippines. The NLRP consists of five key sub-programs, each meticulously designed to target specific aspects of the learning recovery process: the National Learning Camp (NLC), the National Reading Program (NRP), the National Mathematics Program (NMP), and the National Science and Technology Program (NSciTP).

As a comprehensive intervention approach, National Learning Camp (NLC) is intended to give students opportunity for both holistic development and catchup learning. It focuses on improving their socioemotional abilities, academic capabilities, and values formation through a variety of activities carried out in an environment like to a camp. This policy guideline's emphasis on learner-centered approaches is one of its standout features. Through stimulating activities that enhance critical thinking abilities, creativity, teamwork, and communication skills while promoting good values like cooperation and respect for diversity. National Learning Camp was designed to improve learning in the form of enhancement, consolidation, or intervention programs in all learning areas for kindergarten to grade 12 learners and enhance teacher capacity.

Adherence to DepEd Order No. 014, s. 2023 of the Department of Education under the title Policy Guidelines for the National Learning Camp (NLC) Implementation, supported by memorandum issued by the Department of Education(2024) DM-OUCT-2024-097(2024) bearing the title Specific Guidelines for the Effective Implementation of the National Learning Camp and Other Activities for the 2024 end-of-the-school year (EOSY) Break. This was also replicated in the Tabaco City Division through the issuance of Division Memorandum no. 185, s. 2024, known as the Specific Guidelines for the Effective Implementation of the National Learning Camp and Other Activities for the 2024 End-of-the-School Year (EOSY) Break.

Elementary and secondary schools in Tabaco City Division actively cooperated by encouraging learners to participate in the National Learning Camp following the specific guidelines set in the Department of Education Order No. 014, s.2023 (Implementing guidelines for the (National Learning Continuity) NLC). In elementary school, key stage 1 learners were encouraged to join in the National learning Camp (NLC) 2024 to improve their performance in both numeracy and literacy.

The result of this study is crucial for several compelling reasons. First, this initiative aims to address significant gaps in student learning outcomes, particularly in underserved areas. By closely examining its implementation, we can assess the program's effectiveness in reaching these students and identify any challenges that might hinder its success. Understanding the local context of Tabaco City Division is essential in determining how the program can be tailored to best serve the unique needs of its students, teachers, and community.

Furthermore, studying the implementation allows for real-time monitoring, ensuring that the program remains on track and aligned with its educational goals. This also offers an opportunity to gather valuable feedback, enabling necessary adjustments that could improve its long-term impact.

2. Conclusion

The effective implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) needs various factors to be considered. This includes teacher volunteers, teaching methodologies, stakeholders' engagement, and learning resources. In addition to this, problems encountered should also be taken into consideration. Effective implementation of the National Learning Camp (NLC) program competently addresses the learning gaps and improves academic performance of learners.

References

- [1] UNICEF. Children in Gaza need life-saving support. <https://www.unicef.org/education>.
- [2] UNESCO et al. (2022). From Learning Recovery to Learning Transformation. <https://www.unicef.org/media/127291/file/From>
- [3] World Bank Group. (2022). Accelerating learning recovery. World Bank. <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/>.
- [4] Department of Education. (2023). DepEd Order No. 13, s. 2023: National Learning Recovery Program (NLRP). <https://www.deped.gov.ph/>.

- [5] Department of Education (2023). DepEd Order No. 14, s.2023. Policy Guidelines on The Implementation of The National Learning Camp. <https://www.deped.gov.ph/>.
- [6] Department of Education (2024). DM-OUCT-2024-097. Specific Guidelines for the Effective Implementation of the National Learning Camp and Other Activities for the 2024 End-of-the-School-Year (EOSY) Break. <https://www.depedtambayanph.net/>.
- [7] R. M. Pangilinan & L. L. Sarmiento (2021). Volunteer teachers and their contributions to education in underserved areas in the Philippines. *Journal of Educational Research and Practice*.
- [8] Anderson (2024). Revised Bloom's Taxonomy. https://quincycollege.edu/wp-content/uploads/Anderson-and-Krathwohl_Revised-Blooms-Taxonomy.pdf.
- [9] C. Auerbach (2020). Student participation in education: A key to enhancing learning and outcomes. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 45(3), 215-228. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jedu.2020.03.004>.
- [10] J. Smith & A. Jones (2021). Developing and implementing effective intervention plans for at-risk students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 39(2), 115-130. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000512>.